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Physiological effects of the induction of resistance by compost or *Trichoderma asperellum* strain T34 against *Botrytis cinerea* in tomato

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1 **Essential title page information**

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3 Physiological effects of the induction of resistance by compost or *Trichoderma asperellum*

4 strain T34 against *Botrytis cinerea* in tomato

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15 **Abstract**

16 Certain types of compost used as growth media can induce resistance to foliar pathogens in
17 above-ground parts of a plant. The induction of resistance can sometimes be associated with
18 growth impairment and yield reduction. The objective of this study was to establish whether
19 plants grown in olive marc compost had enhanced resistance against *Botrytis cinerea* at the
20 cost of growth or physiological performance.

21 Tomato plants grown in mature olive marc compost had approximately 60% less disease
22 severity than plants grown in perlite. As a reference, plants grown in perlite enriched with the
23 known inducer of resistance *Trichoderma asperellum* strain T34 (T34) had 35 % less disease
24 severity than plants grown in perlite. The salicylic acid (SA) pathway/ abscisic acid (ABA) is
25 involved in compost induced systemic resistance. Instead, perlite enriched with T34 is not
26 linked to SA pathway/ABA. Physiological measures of water status, root/shoot ratio, stable
27 isotopes of C and chlorophyll fluorescence showed that the plants grown in compost were
28 close to a stress situation. However, growth measured as biomass and plant height of plants
29 grown in compost was higher than in plants grown in perlite suggesting that plants in compost
30 were not grown in a stress situation, but in a eustress. Tomato plants grown in perlite enriched
31 with T34 had better growth, measured as total leaf area, biomass, height and nutrient uptake,
32 than plants grown in perlite. Physiological measures showed that plants grown either in perlite
33 or perlite enriched with T34 did not show any abiotic stress situation.

34

35

36 **Keywords:**37 Eustress; Induced plant disease resistance; Olive marc compost; *Solanum lycopersicum*;

38 Stable isotopes

39

40 1. Introduction

41 *Botrytis cinerea* Persoon: Fries, teleomorph *Botryotinia fuckeliana* (de Bary) Whetzel is a
42 plant pathogenic fungus of economic relevance, since it can infect over 200 plant species.
43 This fungus is also known as grey mold and is one of the most extensively studied
44 necrotrophic fungal pathogens. According to Dean et al. (2012), this pathogen was rated the
45 second most important in an international survey of fungal pathologists. Specific fungicide
46 (botryticide) applications and broad spectrum fungicides are the most common method to
47 control this disease. However, fungicide resistance is becoming an important problem (De
48 Ward et al., 2006; Leroch et al., 2011). Moreover, Directive 2009/128/EC will implement
49 integrated pest and disease management in Europe by 2014.

50 The tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* [Miller 1768], *Solanum lycopersicum* [Linné 1753])
51 crop is the eighth largest in the world in terms of food and agricultural commodities
52 production, according to the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO)
53 (<http://faostat.fao.org/site/339/default.aspx>). Spain occupies ninth position in the world in
54 value and production of tomato. This crop is susceptible to *B. cinerea*, which leads to losses
55 during production (greenhouse) and post-harvest. The tomato crop was also selected for this
56 study because it is classified as moderately tolerant to salinity (yield decline at a threshold
57 value of 2.5 mS cm⁻¹) (Maas and Hoffman, 1977). The growth medium evaluated in this
58 study is alperujo compost characterized by basic pH and high electrical conductivity (EC) that
59 may not be optimal for plant cultivation. Therefore, some compost requires formulation with
60 other materials like peat, perlite, coconut fiber, etc. (Cotxarrera et al., 2002). Spain generates a
61 large amount of horticultural residues, such as alperujo, which is waste from the olive oil
62 industry. Alperujo is highly contaminating, acidic, and rich in nutrients (K and N) and
63 lignocellulosic organic matter and has a high fat; carbohydrate and water-soluble phenol
64 content (Albuquerque et al., 2004). Alperujo is a mixture of dregs (liquid that emerges from

65 the olive paste) and marc (pits, skins and pulp). Alperujo can be composted by the addition of
66 olive tree leaves and manure and can be used in agriculture as growth media, amendments or
67 fertilizer. Composts can promote plant growth by nutrition improvement (Bugbee and Finck,
68 1989; Gallardo-Lara and Nogales, 1987; Zhang et al., 2012).

69 Hoitink et al. (1997) proposed that some types of compost naturally suppress certain plant
70 pathogens. The first studies showed that microorganisms played an important role, with
71 antagonistic interactions (competition, hyperparasitism and antibiosis) between the pathogens
72 and the beneficial microorganisms (Cotxarrera et al., 2002; Hoitink et al., 1997; Hoitink and
73 Boehm, 1999; Sant et al., 2010). Moreover, some authors have claimed that certain types of
74 compost used as growth media can induce resistance to foliar pathogens in above-ground
75 parts of a plant, as the microbial populations of the compost are spatially separated (Abbasi et
76 al., 2002; Horst et al., 2005; Kavroulakis et al., 2005; Yogev et al., 2010). This spatially
77 separation is an indirect evidence of the induction of plant resistance and also could be
78 attributed to improved nutrition in plants (Abbasi et al., 2002; De Meyer et al., 1998; Horst et
79 al., 2005; Segarra et al., 2007b; Yogev et al., 2010). A significant increase in peroxidase
80 activity was observed in plants grown in compost vs. plants grown in peat (Zhang et al.,
81 1998), which suggests that compost affects a plant's defense mechanisms. Knowledge about
82 the induction of systemic resistance has been accumulating in recent years, mostly in
83 microbials (plant growth promoting rhizobacteria [PGPR]- and fungal biological control
84 agents) (Durrant and Dong, 2004; Mathys et al., 2012; Pieterse et al., 1996; Ryals et al., 1996;
85 Segarra et al., 2009; Van Loon, 1997; Van Loon et al., 1998). In this study, we used
86 *Trichoderma asperellum* strain T34 as a reference, as it is known to induce priming and
87 systemic resistance (ISR) against other bacterial and fungal diseases, also in other
88 necrotrophic fungi in Arabidopsis plants (Segarra et al., 2009). Moreover, the induction of

89 resistance by T34 is a concentration depending phenomena and plants use the route of ISR or
90 SAR (Segarra et al., 2006, 2007a).

91 The main phytohormones involved in plants defense mechanisms are salicylic acid (SA),
92 jasmonic acid (JA), ethylene (ET) and abscisic acid (ABA) (Pieterse et al., 2012; Vos et al.,
93 2013). Mainly, SA signaling pathway is related with plant resistance against biotrophic and
94 hemibiotrophic pathogens (Vos et al., 2013). However, plant resistance against necrotrophic
95 pathogens as *B. cinerea*, is related with JA signaling pathway (Birkenbihl and Somssich,
96 2011; Vos et al., 2013). Recently, we showed that mature compost from olive oil residues
97 induced resistance against *B. cinerea* in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and that the enhanced resistance
98 was mainly related to processes mediated by SA and ABA, with responses similar to systemic
99 acquired resistance (SAR) and abiotic stress responses (Segarra et al., 2013b). Various studies
100 suggest that SAR can be associated with growth impairment and yield reduction (Denancé et
101 al., 2013; Walters and Heil, 2007). ABA has recently been reported to cross talk with SA and
102 JA in plant disease and defense (Robert-Seilaniatz et al., 2011). ABA has been regarded more
103 as a modulator rather than a primary hormone in plant defense (Ton et al, 2009). The role of
104 ABA is still unclear, because it sometimes appears to promote disease, while at other times it
105 does the opposite.

106 The objective of this study was to establish whether tomato plants grown in compost had
107 enhanced resistance against *B. cinerea* at the cost of growth or physiological performance.

108 2. Materials and methods

109 2.1. Growth media

110 The growth media used were: mature olive marc compost (CM) produced at the University
111 of Seville; perlite (P), an inert mineral growth medium obtained from Europerlite was used as
112 a standard substrate; perlite enriched with the biological control agent *T. asperellum* strain
113 T34 (P+T34) was used as a positive control of resistance induction.

114 CM compost was selected from five different olive marc composts from Andalucía (South
115 Spain) because in a previous study it was demonstrated that did not require formulation to
116 obtain similar germination of *S. lycopersicum* cv. Roma to the perlite control. Compost CM
117 was produced by turned piles and was mature (2 years of stabilization). The composition of
118 CM was olive marc 47% and leaf residues 53% and had a pH of 7.74 and an EC of 0.37 mS
119 cm^{-1} . Perlite was composed of SiO_2 (73%) and Al_2O_3 (13%) and had a pH of 6.69 and an EC
120 of 0.12 mS cm^{-1} . To prepare P+T34, perlite was inoculated with *T. asperellum* strain T34 at a
121 concentration of 10^4 CFU mL^{-1} growth media by dilution on nutrient solution of the
122 concentrated commercial product at 10^9 CFU g^{-1} growth media. After the incubation period
123 the concentration of T34 was about 10 times higher. It was then incubated at a water tension
124 of 1000 Pa (adjusted by weight) at 25°C for 14 days. In order to standardize initial conditions
125 of microbial biomass, P and 4°C stored CM were incubated for the same time and in the same
126 conditions as P+T34.

127

128 2.2. Plant growth studies

129 Tomato plants (*S. lycopersicum* cv. Roma) were sown in 15 mL multipots for 15 days.
130 Subsequently, the plants were transplanted to 250 mL pots in each growth media for 20 days
131 (the end of the experiment). Multipots and pots were placed in a growth chamber ($25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$,
132 16 hours [h] of light at $180\text{--}210 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ photosynthetic photon flux density [PPFD] and

133 60-80% relative humidity [RH]). Plants were hand irrigated on the media as needed (50 and
134 100 mL solution mL⁻¹ medium day⁻¹ in the multipot and pot period, respectively) with the
135 following nutrient solution: 0.5 g L⁻¹ Peter's Foliar Feed 27-15-12 (Scotts), 0.22 g L⁻¹ CaCl₂
136 and 0.25 g L⁻¹ MgSO₄ 7 H₂O.

137 2.2.1. Plant analysis

138 The plant biomass analysis was performed twice in two separate studies and 4 replicates
139 per treatment were used in each study. Shoots, leaves and roots were separated and dried
140 (forced air oven) at 60°C for 48 h. We determined the dry weight of shoots and leaves
141 (DWA), the dry weight of whole plant (DWT), the plant height (H), the root/shoot ratio, and
142 the percentage of water in each plant.

143 We determined the leaf mineral composition analysis according to Segarra et al. (2007b),
144 using dried leaves from two separate studies and 3 replicates per treatment in each study. An
145 aliquot of 50 mg per sample was digested with 2 mL of concentrated HNO₃ and 2mL of H₂O₂
146 in a Teflon container at 90°C for 3 days. Analyses of Ca, K, Si, Mg, Fe, P and S were
147 performed by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) using
148 Optima-3200RL (Perkin Elmer). Analyses of Ni, Mo, B, Cu, Zn and Mn were performed by
149 inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) using Elan 6000 (Perkin Elmer).
150 The carbon and nitrogen percentage and the stable isotope ratios of carbon (¹³C/¹²C) and
151 nitrogen (¹⁵N/¹⁴N) for leaves and roots were determined using an elemental analyzer
152 (EA1108, Series 1, Carlo Erba Instruments) coupled to an isotopic ratio mass spectrometer
153 (IRMS, Delta C, Finnigan MAT). Three leaves and roots per treatments were used from the
154 last study. Leaves and roots were ground separately (to pass through a 1 mm sieve) and
155 aliquots of 0.50 mg were weighed in tin cups and analyzed by the EA-IRMS. The ¹³C/¹²C and
156 ¹⁵N/¹⁴N ratios were expressed as δ notation (δ¹³C and δ¹⁵N respectively), as described by
157 Coplen (2008): δ = [(Isotope Ratio_{Sample}/Isotope Ratio_{Standard})-1] x 1000 (‰). The standard

158 used to calculate $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ was Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite (VPDB) calcium carbonate, and to
159 calculate $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ was N_2 in air. In both measurements, international isotope secondary standards
160 were used to obtain an analytical precision of 0.1‰.

161 Leaf gas exchange and fluorescence analysis was performed on attached tomato leaves.
162 The youngest fully expanded leaves were used (adaxial side). Four plants per treatment were
163 used from the last study for each measure. An infrared gas analyzer (LI-6400, Li-Cor Inc.)
164 was used to measure net CO_2 assimilation rates (A) and stomatal conductance (Gs), using
165 equations developed by Von Caemmerer and Farquhar (1981). Plants were exposed to
166 decreasing PPFD at 1200, 900, 300 and 85 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ at 25°C and 400 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{mol}^{-1}$.
167 Chlorophyll fluorescence was analyzed with an Imaging-PAM fluorometer (Walz). Plants
168 were first dark-adapted for 20 minutes and a saturating light pulse was applied to determine
169 the maximum quantum efficiency of Photosystem II (PSII) (F_v/F_m) (F_v , variable
170 fluorescence; F_m , maximum fluorescence yield in the dark-adapted state). Later, every leaf
171 was adapted for 5 minutes to an actinic light of PPFD at 228 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (similar to the mean
172 growth PPFD). Then, a second saturating light pulse was used to calculate: the relative
173 quantum efficiency of PSII electron transport (Φ_{PSII}) estimated from $\Phi_{\text{PSII}}=(F_m'-F)/F_m'$ (F_m' ,
174 maximum fluorescence yield in the light-adapted state; F, fluorescence yield) according to
175 Genty et al. (1989); the coefficient of photochemical quenching (qP) estimated from
176 $qP=(F_m'-F)/(F_m'-F_0')$ (F_0' , minimum fluorescence yield in the light-adapted state); and the
177 non-photochemical coefficient (qN) estimated from $qN=(F_m-F_m')/(F_m-F_0')$ (Andrews et al.,
178 1993). The parameter F_0' was estimated using an approximation by Oxborough and Baker
179 (1997).

180 Total leaf area (TLA), specific leaf weight (SLW) and relative water content (RWC) were
181 used from leaves after monitoring gas exchange measures. TLA was determined using a
182 scanner, Image leaf area measurement software (University of Sheffield, 2003), and dry

183 weight. SLW was calculated from $SLW = DW/TLA$ and the RWC was determined according
184 to Turner (1981).

185

186 2.3. Plant disease studies

187 Tomato plants were grown in the same conditions as mentioned for the plant growth
188 studies up to day 15 of transplantation to 250 mL pots. On that day, plants were placed in
189 mini-tunnels (inside the growth chamber) to establish the best conditions for *B. cinerea*
190 disease. The growth chamber was modified to obtain the following conditions inside the mini-
191 tunnels: 24°C (day) and 20°C (night), 16 h light and near 100% RH. Plants were adapted to
192 the new environmental conditions one day before inoculation with the pathogen. The number
193 of plants in each of the three growth media was 14: 5 (controls) without pathogen inoculation,
194 and 9 with pathogen-inoculated leaves. The control plants were placed in separate mini-
195 tunnels to the inoculated plants, each of which was grown in a different mini tunnel. The
196 experiment was repeated three times.

197 2.3.1. Pathogen inoculation

198 A virulent strain of *B. cinerea* isolated from tomato-infected leaves and stored in silica gel
199 crystals at 4°C was cultivated in mixed vegetable solid medium for 21 days at 20°C, 7 days
200 under dark conditions, and 14 days at PPFD 85 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and 16 h light. The mixed
201 vegetable medium was prepared by cooking 500 g of a commercial frozen mix of potato,
202 carrot and beans in water. The boiled vegetables and cooking water were homogenized with a
203 kitchen blender, the volume was brought to 1 L and 150 mL of the mixture plus 7.5 g of agar
204 were used to prepare 500 mL of mixed vegetable medium. Conidia were collected from the
205 plates in an inoculation buffer containing 0.5 mg mL⁻¹ glucose and 0.5 mg mL⁻¹ KH₂PO₄ (De
206 Meyer et al., 1998). Twelve mL of the buffer was used per plate; the resulting suspension was
207 filtered through two cotton gauzes. The concentration of *B. cinerea* was adjusted to 10⁵

208 conidia mL⁻¹ by hemocytometer counting. Finally, a drop of Tween 20 was added to the
209 inoculum (0.005%) to promote uniform dispersion of the inoculum on plants leaves. Two
210 expanded leaves from each plant were sprayed with approximately 550 µL per leaf with a low
211 pressure plastic hand sprayer.

212 2.3.2. Assessment of disease

213 The severity and incidence of disease was examined 7, 10 and 14 days post-inoculation.
214 Severity was evaluated using the following score for each leaf: 0 (asymptomatic), 1 (chlorotic
215 spots), 2 (necrotic specks), 3 (necrotic spots), 4 (dead leaf). The area under the disease
216 progress curve (AUDPC) per leaf was calculated by disease severity as described by Shaner
217 and Finney (1977). The AUDPC was standardized by dividing with the total area of the graph
218 (total days of observing disease symptoms multiplied by the maximum degree of disease).
219 Disease incidence was evaluated as: 0, healthy; 1, infected. Disease incidence was calculated
220 as the percentage of diseased leaves.

221 2.3.3. Plant hormone analysis

222 The plant hormones SA, ABA and JA were quantified as follows. The first fully expanded
223 tomato leaf of each plant was sampled on day 0, 1, 3 and 5 post-pathogen inoculation. Three
224 plants per treatment were used from the last study. The leaf from each plant was collected
225 separately and quick-frozen in liquid N₂. Frozen samples were ground under liquid N₂ with a
226 mortar and pestle. A total of 50 mg of the resulting powder was first extracted and twice re-
227 extracted with methanol: isopropanol: acetic acid (20:79:1, v/v/v) (Müller and Munné-Bosh,
228 2011). The extracted samples were quantified according to Segarra et al. (2006), using the
229 following transitions: 137/93, 263/153 and 209/59 for SA, ABA and JA respectively.

230

231 2.4. Experimental design and statistical analysis

232 Data were analyzed by IBM SPSS Statistics 19 version statistical software. Data from plant
233 growth studies that were performed twice (DWA, DWT, Root/Shoot, H, Total H₂O, mineral
234 composition) were analyzed using a multifactorial ANOVA ($p < 0.05$). The factor experiment
235 and the interaction with the factor treatment were not significant, so data from the various
236 experiments were pooled. Hence, data was analyzed with a unifactorial ANOVA to study the
237 factor treatment for each growth and physiological parameter analyzed (DWA, DWT,
238 root/shoot, H, Total H₂O, mineral composition, C/N ratio, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, A, Gs Fv/Fm, ϕ_{PSII} , qP,
239 qN, TLA, SLW and RWC). When significant differences were observed ($p < 0.05$), the
240 Duncan's multiple range test was performed ($p < 0.05$). Data from disease assessments (DS, DI
241 and AUDPC) that were performed three times were also analyzed using a multifactorial
242 ANOVA ($p < 0.05$). The factor experiment and the interaction with the factor treatment were
243 not significant. Therefore, data from the three experiments were also pooled. Consequently,
244 data from disease assessments (DS, DI and AUDPC) and plant hormone analyses (SA, ABA
245 and JA) were analyzed with a unifactorial ANOVA to study the factor treatment over the
246 evaluation days. When significant differences were observed ($p < 0.05$), the Duncan's multiple
247 range test was performed ($p < 0.05$). In cases in which normal distribution and homogeneity of
248 variances were not found, the Kruskal-Wallis test was performed ($p < 0.05$). Relationships
249 between DS, DI and AUDPC and plant physiological parameters and plant hormone content
250 were analyzed with the Pearson correlation coefficient ($p < 0.05$).

251

252 **3. Results**

253 3.1. Effect of substrate on plant growth and physiological performance

254 The overall plant growth measured as DWA and DWT was higher in plants grown in
255 P+T34 and in CM than in P alone (Table 1). The root/shoot ratio was higher in P and in
256 P+T34 than in CM. Plants grown in P+T34 developed a higher TLA than in the other
257 treatments, and the SLW (g m^{-2}) was the same for all leaves (data not shown). The lowest
258 plant height was found in plants grown in P, followed by P+T34. Plants grown in CM were
259 the highest. Leaf water status, measured as RWC, was higher in leaves grown on P and
260 P+T34 than in CM. A similar pattern was obtained when the water content was measured in
261 the whole plant (roots, shoots and leaves) (Table 1).

262 The Ca composition in leaves was higher in plants grown in CM than in the rest of the
263 growth media (Table 2). The overall mineral composition of Mg, P, B and Cu was higher in
264 plants grown in P+T34, followed by P, whilst the lowest values were found in plants grown in
265 CM. Plants grown in P+T34 and P had the highest Fe, Mn and Mo levels in leaves. The
266 lowest Fe, Mn and Mo levels were obtained in plants grown in CM. No significant differences
267 among treatments were observed in K, S, Si and Zn levels in leaves (Table 2). The ratio C/N
268 in the leaves was higher in plants grown in CM than in P+T34 and P. The ratio C/N in the
269 roots was the same for plants in all plant growth media (Table 2).

270 The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of leaves of plants grown in CM was less negative than in plants grown in P+T34
271 and P (Table 3). The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of roots was also less negative in CM, followed by P+T34, whilst
272 the most negative values were found in P. The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of leaves was higher in plants grown in
273 CM than in the rest of the growth media. The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of roots was higher in plants grown in
274 P+T34, followed by P and the lowest values were found in compost CM (Table 3).

275 Leaves of tomato plants grown in the different growth media showed an increase in the net
276 CO_2 assimilation rate (A), according to an increase in PPFD from 85 to saturation levels 1200

277 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. No significant differences among treatments were observed below 1200 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}$
278 s^{-1} PPFD. Plants grown in CM showed the highest rate (Figure 1). The results for A are in
279 agreement with the Gs. The highest Gs and A values were observed in plants grown in CM.
280 The lowest levels of Gs and A were observed in plants grown in P and P+T34. At 1200 μmol
281 $\text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ of PPFD plants grown in P+T34 showed a significant decrease measured in both A and
282 Gs (Figure 1).

283 The fluorescence analysis showed that the highest values of Fv/Fm were observed in plants
284 grown in P+T34, followed by plants grown in P alone, whilst the lowest values were observed
285 in plants grown in CM (Table 4). No significant differences among treatments were observed
286 in Φ_{PSII} and qP. The highest values of qN were in plants grown in P and P+T34, being the
287 lowest values in CM plants (Table 4).

288

289 3.2. Effect of substrate on *Botrytis* disease control

290 Tomato plants grown on compost CM showed the lowest levels of disease, measured as
291 disease severity (DS) (lower than 1, on a scale from 0 to 4), disease incidence (DI) (from
292 57,5-72,5%) from 7 to 14 days and AUDPC (0.20 ± 0.03) (Table 5). Plants growing in P
293 showed a DS from 2.07 to 3.36, a DI of around 100% and a AUDPC of 0.72 ± 0.02 . P+T34
294 improved the suppression to levels between those of CM and P, as shown in the values
295 attained for DS and AUDPC (Table 5). Negative correlations ($p < 0.05$) were attained for
296 disease (DS on day 14 and AUDPC) and plant growth parameters such as the DWA, H, C/N
297 shoots, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of roots and Gs at 1200 and 900 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ of PPFD. Moreover, negative
298 correlations ($p < 0.05$) were attained for DI on day 14 and C/N shoots. Positive correlations
299 ($p < 0.05$) were attained for disease (DS on day 14 and AUDPC) and plant growth parameters
300 such as root/shoot ratio and qN. Moreover, positive correlations ($p < 0.05$) were attained for DI
301 on day 14 and root/shoot ratio. The hormone quantification of SA, ABA and JA did not show

302 significant differences between treatments on day 0 (previous to inoculation of the leaves with
303 the pathogen) (Table 6). The SA concentration of infected leaves of plants grown in compost
304 CM significantly increased on day 1 post-inoculation, and was higher than in plants grown in
305 P and P+T34. On days 3 and 5 post-inoculation, the SA levels of CM still were higher than in
306 the rest of treatments. On day 5, leaves of plants grown in P and P+T34 decreased similarly or
307 below the levels of day 0. The ABA concentration in leaves of plants grown in compost CM
308 on day 1 was higher than the rest of treatments, followed by P, whilst the lowest values were
309 found in leaves of plants grown in P+T34. On days 3 and 5, ABA levels of all treatments
310 decreased similarly or below the levels of day 0 and there were no differences among
311 treatments (Table 6). The JA concentration was the same along the days of the study and for
312 all treatments (Table 6). Negative correlations ($p < 0.05$) were attained for disease (DS and DI
313 on day 14 and AUDPC) and plant hormone status, such as SA on days 1 and 3 and ABA on
314 day 1. Furthermore, negative correlations ($p < 0.05$) were attained for DI on day 14 and plant
315 ABA status on day 5.

316

317 **4. Discussion**

318 The beneficial effect of composts on plant growth is well-documented (Arthur et al., 2012;
319 Gallardo-Lara and Nogales, 1987; Zhang et al., 2012) and was also observed in this study on
320 tomato plants grown in compost, compared to those grown in perlite. The high pH (7.7) of
321 CM could explain the lower levels of several mineral elements (Mg, P, Fe, Mn, Zn and Cu) in
322 the plants. No difference was observed in the leaf nutrients when the same compost CM was
323 used in *A. thaliana* plants (Segarra et al., 2013a). The highest levels of Ca in compost CM
324 could explain, in part, the involvement of this element in the reduction of gray mold disease
325 caused by *B. cinerea*. Indeed, high levels of Ca in leaves have been associated with foliar
326 disease resistance (Wójcik and Lewandowski, 2003). In several studies, Ca is involved in
327 biotic and abiotic stress responses (Segarra et al., 2007b), callose synthesis (Trillas et al.,
328 2000), pectin binding molecules (Carpita and McCann, 2000), SA (Schneider-Müller et al.,
329 1994) and phytoalexin synthesis (Vögeli et al., 1992).

330 The lower water status (RWC and total water) of plants grown in compost could be due to
331 the EC of compost, which might have an inhibitory effect on Botrytis development.
332 According to Mayak et al. (2004), RWC is an adequate indicator of water status in plants and
333 is characterized by a decrease in stress conditions (drought and salinity). The pH and EC of
334 olive marc compost were similar to those of other kinds of compost and other samples of the
335 same type (Borrero et al., 2004; Cotxarrera et al., 2002; Segarra et al., 2007b). In one study,
336 the RWC of tomato plants grown with high irradiation in a high EC solution was reduced to
337 81.5% (Claussen, 2005).

338 All measures of plant biomass were higher for tomato plants grown in P+T34 than in P
339 alone; and the results were similar to those of plants grown in compost. The use of beneficial
340 microorganisms in the rhizosphere (bacteria and fungus) can facilitate solubility, enhance the
341 availability of nutrients to plants from the nutrient solution (Altomare et al., 1999), and

342 protect against biotic stress. The most relevant characteristic of plants grown in P+T34 was
343 the greater investment in leaf area. This could explain the greater accumulation of most of the
344 elements, especially Mg, P, B and Cu in the leaves. In particular, Mg, P and Cu are involved
345 in key reactions in leaves energetic processes. The increased uptake of Mg^{2+} and P was also
346 observed in tomato shoots and roots grown in soil amended with *T. harzianum* strain T447
347 (Azarmi et al., 2011). Whereas in a study with *T. harzianum* strain T-203 increased uptake of
348 Cu was observed in roots and not leaves of cucumber plants (Yedidia et al., 2001). Moreover,
349 the principal function of B is a structural role related to the stability of the cell wall (O'Neill
350 et al., 2004). Accordingly greater amount of B could improve plant resistance to *B. cinerea*
351 attack.

352 The highest C/N ratio of plants grown in compost showed the lowest content of nitrogen in
353 leaves, which would make the leaves more resistant to attack by the pathogen. Conversely, in
354 a study with tomato plants with high C/N ratio makes plants more susceptible to the primary
355 lesions formation caused by *B. cinerea* (Hoffland et al., 1999). The role of host nitrogen
356 content in the susceptibility to *B. cinerea* is still unclear because there are other factors
357 involved as N source and amount and *B. cinerea* isolates virulence (Lecompte et al., 2010).

358 Our study of stable isotopes of $\delta^{13}C$ and $\delta^{15}N$ clearly distinguishes the roots of plants
359 grown in P from those grown on P+T34. This suggests that the same C assimilation occurs,
360 but the post-photosynthetic fractionation of stable carbone isotopes between leaves and roots
361 and N assimilation by roots in contact with T34 differs. Makarov (2009) have observed that
362 mycorrhizal fungi are involved in determining the plant $\delta^{15}N$. In a similar way, T34 could be
363 involved in determining tomato plants $\delta^{15}N$ probably by improving the availability of this
364 element to plants. Several studies have shown that $\delta^{13}C$ increase or carbon isotope
365 discrimination decrease in water deficit conditions (Condon et al., 2002; Ehleringer and
366 Cooper, 1988; Farquhar et al., 1982; Yousfi et al., 2009). Similarly, in our study, plants grown

367 in compost were characterized by the lowest water status and also showed the highest $\delta^{13}\text{C}$,
368 probably related to a certain degree of stress due to compost EC. In contrast, the effect of
369 water status in $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ differs between studies (Handley et al., 1997; Lopes and Araus, 2006).
370 The diverse composition of the growth media could explain the lowest $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ in CM. Despite
371 this, according to Mariotti et al. (1982) the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ signature of the source of N is not the only
372 factor determining plant $\delta^{15}\text{N}$.

373 The data for photosynthesis and chlorophyll fluorescence were similar for tomato plants
374 grown in a growth chamber at a similar age (Nogués et al., 2002). Measures of photosynthesis
375 showed that plants grown in CM behave as plants grown at high light intensity (measure
376 carried out at $1200 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ PPFD). This value contrasts with that found for plants grown
377 in all other treatments, which were saturated at this light level. Measures of chlorophyll
378 fluorescence were similar among treatments and the Fv/Fm ratios in all treatments were over
379 0.75, which is considered the limit for photoinhibition (Björkman and Demmig, 1987).

380 All these data confirm that plants were grown properly in all growth media, although
381 plants grown in CM were near to the limits of stress conditions (lowest root/shoot ratio,
382 RWC, total water, Fv/Fm and highest $\delta^{13}\text{C}$). Growth parameters and physiological measures
383 of plants grown in CM suggests that the plants had grown in a eustress situation. According to
384 Hideg et al. (2012), eustress is considered mild and acclimative stress that improves growth
385 and health. It is the opposite of distress or severe stress, which exceeds tolerance limits and
386 leads to the death of plants.

387 Our results showed the suppressive capacity of mature olive marc compost CM in reducing
388 the severity and incidence of *B. cinerea* and in inducing systemic resistance. The induction of
389 systemic resistance was also linked to SA (which only increased after pathogen exposure).
390 Although *B. cinerea* is a necrotrophic pathogen and triggers mainly the JA signaling pathway
391 and not the SA signaling pathway (Birkenbihl and Somssich, 2011; Vos et al., 2013). Indirect

392 evidence of the induction of resistance has been observed previously in composted cannery
393 wastes against anthracnose tomato rot disease (Abbasi et al., 2002); in composted cow
394 manure against *B. cinerea* in *Begonia hiemalis* (Horst et al., 2005); and in grape marc
395 compost, olive marc-cotton gin trash (1:1, v:v) compost, cork compost, municipal organic and
396 yard waste compost and spent mushroom compost against *B. cinerea* in *Cucumis sativus*
397 (Segarra et al., 2007b). In another study, disease reduction was also induced by SAR using
398 composted pine bark mix inoculated with *Trichoderma hamatum* 382 and *Flavobacterium*
399 *balustinum* 299 and compost water extract against anthracnose and against bacterial speck in
400 cucumber plants (Zhang et al., 1998). The spatial separation between the biological control
401 agent (T34) and the pathogen and the reduction of *Botrytis* disease showed the involvement of
402 the induction of plant resistance, even though an increase in JA levels could not be detected
403 by T34 in the evaluated days of this study. Indeed, T34 applied to the roots has been shown to
404 prime for induced resistance independently of SA (Segarra et al., 2009; Trillas and Segarra,
405 2009). However, SA increases have only been found when high concentrations (laboratory
406 levels, not field levels) of T34 are applied (10^7 CFU mL⁻¹) (Segarra et al., 2007a).

407 Various studies suggest that ABA is involved in disease reduction or increase, according to
408 the type of pathogen (Robert-Seilaniatz et al., 2011). ABA-deficient *A. thaliana* mutants were
409 more resistant to *B. cinerea*, but more susceptible to *Pythium irregulare* (Adie et al., 2007).
410 Similarly, ABA-deficient tomato mutants were more resistant to *B. cinerea* (Asselbergh et al.,
411 2007). Ton et al. (2009) describes the role of ABA in plant disease defense more as a
412 modulator rather than a primary hormone. Other studies suggested that the levels of SA, ABA
413 and JA prior to contact with the pathogen had a determining impact on the interaction
414 dynamics between these hormones (Robert-Seilaniatz et al., 2011). Interestingly, ABA levels
415 of plants grown in CM increased after *B. cinerea* exposure. Recent studies from our group
416 corroborate the involvement of both SAR and ABA-dependent/independent abiotic stress

417 responses in *A. thaliana* plants grown in olive marc composts or perlite exposed to *B. cinerea*

418 (Segarra et al., 2013a, 2013b).

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420 **5. Conclusions**

421 In conclusion, physiological parameters measured in tomato plants grown in mature olive
422 marc compost showed no negative influence on plant biomass, CO₂ assimilation rate or
423 chlorophyll fluorescence measurements, plants grew in a eustress situation that might have
424 had a positive influence on disease resistance. The compost induction of systemic resistance
425 was also linked to SA pathway/ABA.

426 Tomato plants growing in perlite enriched with *T. asperellum* strain T34 had better nutrient
427 uptake, better C allocation and N assimilation in roots leading to an improvement in dry
428 weight, height and total leaf area than plants grown in perlite alone. Plants grown in perlite
429 enriched with T34 had no stress effects, measured by the overall physiological parameters.
430 The induction of disease resistance observed in perlite enriched with T34 is not linked to the
431 SA pathway/ABA.

432 By describing the positive effects and the diverse responses of plants grown in compost
433 and perlite enriched with T34, we are contributing to understanding the role of compost and
434 beneficial organisms that help plants to grow healthier and improve their innate resistance
435 to foliar pathogen attacks.

436

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444

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642

643 **Table 1**

644 Effect of growth medium (P, perlite; P+T34, perlite enriched with *Trichoderma asperellum* strain T34 at a
645 concentration of 10^4 CFU mL⁻¹; CM, olive marc compost) on various physiological parameters of tomato plants

646

647 ^a Aerial dry weight (leaves and shoots)648 ^b Total dry weight649 ^c Total leaf area650 ^d Plant height651 ^e Relative water content652 Values of DWA, DWT, Root/Shoot and Total H₂O are means \pm standard error of 8 plants per treatment653 collected from two separate studies (4 replicates each study). Values of TLA, H and RWC are means \pm

654 standard error of 4 plants per treatment collected from one of the studies. Different letters show significant

655 differences $p < 0.05$ on Duncan's multiple range test

656

657

658

659 **Table 2**660 Effect of growth medium (P, perlite; P+T34, perlite enriched with *Trichoderma asperellum* strain T34 at a661 concentration of 10^4 CFU mL⁻¹; CM, olive marc compost) on mineral composition of fully expanded tomato

662 leaves

663

664 Values of macronutrients and micronutrients are means \pm standard error of 6 leaves per treatment collected from665 two separated studies (3 replicates per treatment in each study). Values of C/N are means \pm standard error of 3

666 leaves and roots per treatment collected from one of the studies. Different letters show significant differences

667 $p < 0.05$ on a Duncan's multiple range test

668

669

670

671

672 **Table 3**

673 Effect of growth medium (P, perlite; P+T34, perlite enriched with *Trichoderma asperellum* strain T34 at a
674 concentration of 10^4 CFU mL⁻¹; CM, olive marc compost) on stable isotope ratios of carbon (¹³C/¹²C, expressed
675 as $\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and nitrogen (¹⁵N/¹⁴N express as $\delta^{15}\text{N}$) of leaves and roots of tomato plants

676

677 Values are means \pm standard error of 3 leaves and roots per treatment collected from one of the studies. Different
678 letters show significant differences $p < 0.05$ on a Duncan's multiple range test

679

680

681

682 **Table 4**

683 Effect of growth medium (P, perlite; P+T34, perlite enriched with *Trichoderma asperellum* strain T34 at a
684 concentration of 10^4 CFU mL⁻¹; CM, olive marc compost) on chlorophyll fluorescence of fully expanded tomato
685 leaves

686

687 ^a Maximum quantum efficiency of Photosystem II (PSII)

688 ^b Relative quantum efficiency of PSII

689 ^c Coefficient of photochemical quenching

690 ^d Coefficient of non photochemical quenching

691 Values are means \pm standard error of 4 leaves per treatment collected from one of the studies. Different letters
692 show significant differences $p < 0.05$ on a Duncan's multiple range test

693

694

695

696 **Table 5**

697 Disease severity (DS), disease incidence (DI) (%) and area under disease progress curve (AUDPC) based on DS
698 caused by the pathogen *Botrytis cinerea* (10^5 CFU mL⁻¹) in tomato plants in three independent bioassays. Plants
699 were grown in three growth media: P, perlite; P+T34, perlite enriched with *Trichoderma asperellum* strain T34

700 at a concentration of 10^4 CFU mL⁻¹; CM, olive marc compost. Disease was evaluated at 7, 10 and 14 days post-
701 inoculation (dpi)

702

703 ^a DS evaluated with a scale of five grades: 0, asymptomatic; 1, chlorotic leaf; 2, necrotic specks; 3, necrotic spot;
704 4, dead leaf

705 ^b DI was evaluated as: 0, healthy; 1, infected. DI was calculated as the percentage of diseased leaves

706 ^c AUDPC was standardized by dividing with the total area of the graph (total days of observing disease
707 symptoms per maximum degree of disease)

708 Values are means \pm standard error of 35-54 leaves per treatment collected from three separated studies (6-18
709 replicates per treatment in each study). Different lower case letters show significant differences between
710 treatments and different capital letters show significant difference between days (dpi) within treatments ($p < 0.05$)
711 on an Duncan's multiple range test.

712

713

714

715 **Table 6**

716 Effect of growth medium (P, perlite; P+T34, perlite enriched with *Trichoderma asperellum* strain T34 at a
717 concentration of 10^4 CFU mL⁻¹; CM, olive marc compost) on hormone (SA, salicylic acid, ABA, abscisic acid
718 and JA, jasmonic acid) content in leaves of tomato plants that were not inoculated (0) or inoculated (1, 3, 5 days
719 post-inoculation) with *Botrytis cinerea* (10^5 CFU mL⁻¹)

720

721 Values are means \pm standard error of 2-3 leaves per treatment collected from one of the studies. Different lower
722 case letters show significant differences between treatments and different capital letters show significant
723 difference between days within treatments for each plant hormone ($p < 0.05$) on a Duncan's multiple range test

724

725

726

727 **Figure 1**

728 Photosynthesis response curves to light in fully expanded tomato plant leaves. Measurements were made on 20
729 days post-seeding, in plants grown on three growth media: perlite (P), perlite + *Trichoderma asperellum* strain

730 T34 (P+T34) (10^4 CFU mL⁻¹) and compost (CM). Curves were performed at 25°C, 400 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ CO₂ and at a
731 decreasing photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD) of 1200, 900, 300 and 85 $\mu\text{mol photon m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. (A) Net
732 CO₂ assimilation rate (A, $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) (B) stomatal conductance (Gs, $\text{mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). Values are means
733 \pm standard error of 4 leaves per treatment collected from one of the studies. Different lower case letters show
734 significant differences between treatments and different capital letters show significant difference between days
735 within treatments ($p < 0.05$) on an Duncan's multiple range test.
736

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Table 1

Growth Medium	DWA ^a (g)	DWT ^b (g)	Root/Shoot	TLA ^c (cm ²)	H ^d (cm)	RWC ^e	Total H ₂ O (%)
P	0.14 ± 0.009 a	0.17 ± 0.011 a	0.23 ± 0.010 b	112.52 ± 9.31 a	7.66 ± 0.36 a	90.57 ± 0.88 b	95.21 ± 0.05 b
P+T34	0.25 ± 0.010 b	0.31 ± 0.011 c	0.23 ± 0.018 b	181.52 ± 9.13 b	9.62 ± 0.30 b	89.55 ± 1.64 b	95.07 ± 0.10 b
CM	0.23 ± 0.016 b	0.26 ± 0.020 b	0.12 ± 0.009 a	99.65 ± 9.49 a	10.60 ± 0.28 c	81.66 ± 3.41 a	94.10 ± 0.28 a

Table 2

Growth Medium	Macronutrient (mg planta ⁻¹)													
	K		Ca		Mg		P		S		Si		Fe	
P	7.75 ± 0.90	a	4.89 ± 0.27	a	0.92 ± 0.02	b	1.95 ± 0.05	b	1.01 ± 0.10	a	0.08 ± 0.01	a	0.03 ± 0.00	b
P+T34	9.84 ± 1.33	a	6.12 ± 0.56	a	1.21 ± 0.08	c	2.52 ± 0.08	c	1.25 ± 0.13	a	0.09 ± 0.03	a	0.04 ± 0.00	b
CM	8.10 ± 0.62	a	7.81 ± 0.33	b	0.76 ± 0.02	a	1.21 ± 0.05	a	1.32 ± 0.08	a	0.03 ± 0.01	a	0.02 ± 0.00	a
Growth Medium	Micronutrient (µg planta ⁻¹)										C/N			
	B		Mn		Zn		Cu		Mo		Leaves		Roots	
P	13.53 ± 0.29	b	30.92 ± 3.88	b	12.20 ± 2.04	a	5.73 ± 0.20	b	0.53 ± 0.02	b	5.79 ± 0.14	a	7.93 ± 0.10	a
P+T34	18.42 ± 1.74	c	40.06 ± 6.82	b	16.55 ± 1.93	a	7.89 ± 0.39	c	0.60 ± 0.04	b	6.31 ± 0.19	a	8.05 ± 0.37	a
CM	6.90 ± 0.33	a	14.81 ± 2.00	a	13.81 ± 0.94	a	3.46 ± 0.34	a	0.24 ± 0.02	a	7.19 ± 0.16	b	7.27 ± 0.23	a

Table 3

Growth Medium	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰)		$\delta^{15}\text{N}$ (‰)	
	Leaves	Roots	Leaves	Roots
P	-35.30 \pm 0.17 a	-34.53 \pm 0.10 a	-3.14 \pm 0.12 a	1.94 \pm 0.37 b
P+T34	-34.97 \pm 0.15 a	-34.14 \pm 0.08 b	-2.71 \pm 0.21 a	3.39 \pm 0.26 c
CM	-34.28 \pm 0.11 b	-33.41 \pm 0.13 c	1.22 \pm 0.21 b	0.34 \pm 0.40 a

Table 4

Growth Medium	F_v/F_m^a	Φ_{PSII}^b	qP^c	qN^d
P	0.808 ± 0.001 b	0.497 ± 0.016 a	0.703 ± 0.013 a	0.507 ± 0.034 b
P+T34	0.820 ± 0.005 c	0.514 ± 0.003 a	0.710 ± 0.007 a	0.502 ± 0.010 b
CM	0.793 ± 0.002 a	0.533 ± 0.009 a	0.740 ± 0.013 a	0.402 ± 0.013 a

Table 5

Growth Medium	DS ^a			DI (%) ^b			AUDPC ^c
	7 dpi	10 dpi	14 dpi	7 dpi	10 dpi	14 dpi	
P	2.07 ± 0.08 cA	2.93 ± 0.12 cB	3.36 ± 0.11 cC	100.0 ± 0.00 bA	100.0 ± 0.00 bA	100.0 ± 0.00 bA	0.72 ± 0.02 c
P+T34	1.46 ± 0.08 bA	1.77 ± 0.09 bB	1.94 ± 0.11 bB	97.1 ± 2.86 bA	97.1 ± 2.86 bA	97.1 ± 2.86 bA	0.44 ± 0.02 b
CM	0.62 ± 0.12 aA	0.78 ± 0.13 aA	0.94 ± 0.15 aA	57.5 ± 7.91 aA	65.0 ± 7.64 aA	72.5 ± 7.15 aA	0.20 ± 0.03 a

Table 6

Hormone	Growth Medium	Days post-inoculation							
		0		1		3		5	
SA (ng g ⁻¹ FW)	P	39.50 ± 2.65	aBC	47.53 ± 4.53	aC	33.83 ± 3.37	aB	22.53 ± 1.03	aA
	P+T34	47.10 ± 6.82	aBC	52.53 ± 3.92	aC	33.57 ± 5.70	aAB	25.10 ± 0.59	aA
	CM	49.83 ± 6.20	aAB	103.75 ± 5.35	bC	65.90 ± 10.31	bBC	35.87 ± 4.23	bA
ABA (ng g ⁻¹ FW)	P	161.90 ± 12.49	aC	142.37 ± 2.52	aC	94.17 ± 12.15	aB	58.63 ± 5.42	aA
	P+T34	151.93 ± 11.31	aC	107.30 ± 4.29	bB	79.27 ± 18.41	aAB	51.97 ± 10.94	aA
	CM	251.50 ± 40.55	aB	345.25 ± 1.05	cC	130.50 ± 6.57	aA	115.37 ± 8.47	bA
JA (ng g ⁻¹ FW)	P	1.00 ± 0.10	aA	0.40 ± 0.06	aA	1.03 ± 0.34	aA	0.57 ± 0.12	aA
	P+T34	0.83 ± 0.58	aA	1.50 ± 0.58	aA	0.80 ± 0.11	aA	0.77 ± 0.47	aA
	CM	1.60 ± 0.55	aA	0.90 ± 0.10	aA	0.67 ± 0.12	aA	0.73 ± 0.14	aA

Tomato leaves inoculated with *Botrytis cinerea* (10^2 CFU mL⁻¹)

- (A) Olive marc compost
 (B) Perlite enriched with *Trichoderma asperellum* (10^4 CFU mL⁻¹)
 (C) Perlite

DWA
 Root/Shoot
 Plant Height
 C/N leaves
 $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ roots
 Gs
 qN
 SA
 ABA

+

-

++

++

++

+

-

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+

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739 **Highlights**

- 740 • Compost triggered eustress in tomato plants, improving growth and health
- 741 • Compost induced systemic resistance linked to SA pathway/ABA
- 742 • *Trichoderma*-enriched perlite improved plant growth and innate disease resistance
- 743 • Different mechanisms of induced resistance are involved in compost and *Trichoderma*
- 744

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